

CLINICAL AND AUDIOLOGICAL EFFECTIVENESS OF HEARING IMPROVEMENT SURGERIES IN CHRONIC SUPPURATIVE OTITIS MEDIA AND THEIR IMPACT ON PATIENTS' QUALITY OF LIFE

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Abstract. *The objective of this research is to evaluate the functional outcomes of hearing improvement surgeries in chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM). The functional outcomes of using a partial ossicular replacement prosthesis (PORP) were significantly higher compared to a total ossicular replacement prosthesis (TORP). These results suggest that TORP is used in more severe middle ear conditions, such as stapes structure erosion. The tonal audiogram data after simultaneous and two-stage tympanoplasty in patients with CSOM indicate that simultaneous tympanoplasty with ossiculoplasty is highly effective in CSOM, with hearing outcomes comparable to those of two-stage ossiculoplasty.*

Keywords: *chronic suppurative otitis media, ossiculoplasty.*

Chronic Suppurative Otitis Media is primarily characterized by decreased or lost hearing acuity, otorrhea, ear congestion, tinnitus, and ear pain, as well as headaches. Patients often experience limitations in their ability to communicate due to hearing loss or impairment, which in turn can lead to depression, anxiety, and social isolation [1,2,3,8]. This condition results in a decrease in the health-related quality of life, affecting physical, functional, social, psychological, and family aspects [4,5,6,7].

This study was conducted from 2019 to 2023 at the clinical bases of the Department of "Otorhinolaryngology, Pediatric Otorhinolaryngology, and Pediatric Dentistry" of Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute. All participants were informed and gave their consent to participate in the survey. The study group included participants over 18 years old who were able to complete the forms. Exclusions were made for participants under 18 years of age, those unable to complete the forms, and individuals with mental or chronic systemic diseases.

Objective of the Study: To evaluate the functional outcomes of tympanoplasty with ossiculoplasty and indicators of quality of life in patients with chronic suppurative otitis media by studying clinical and audiological parameters, as well as using the COMOT-15 questionnaire.

Materials and Methods: Patients underwent general clinical, otorhinolaryngological, radiological (MSCT of the temporal bones), audiological examinations, and were surveyed using the COMOT-15 questionnaire—an outpatient test for chronic suppurative otitis media.

The examination included a detailed study of the anamnesis, otoscopy, and all patients underwent clinical evaluations, including endoscopic and microscopic assessments of ENT organs, as well as audiological studies, which included tonal threshold audiometry with measurement of the air-bone gap in both ears. The average value was measured in dB and calculated based on air conduction at 500 Hz, 1000 Hz, 2000 Hz, and 4000 Hz. The WHO classification of hearing loss was used to determine the degree of hearing impairment.

The COMOT-15 questionnaire includes 16 questions divided into three main groups: The first group of questions assesses ear symptoms (ES-ears symptoms); the second group evaluates the patient's hearing function (HF-hearing function); and the third group assesses the patient's mental health (MH-mental health). The overall quality of life (OS) is determined by summing the scores from these three groups (ES + HF + MH = OS). Each question is rated on a 5-point scale.

A detailed characterization of the clinical material and study design is presented below. Patients were divided into two subgroups: patients with CSOM who underwent simultaneous tympanoplasty with ossiculoplasty (35 patients in the 1st group) and 25 patients who underwent two-stage tympanoplasty with ossiculoplasty (2nd group). Complete removal of inflammatory tissue and cholesteatoma from the middle ear was performed, along with ossiculoplasty using titanium and hydroxyapatite prostheses. Partial ossicular replacement prosthesis (PORP) and total ossicular replacement prosthesis (TORP) were used based on the condition of the ossicles, which were assessed during surgery. A partial prosthesis was used if the incus was absent or eroded but the stapes were intact. A total prosthesis was used if the stapes structure was eroded or absent. When using a titanium prosthesis, cartilage was placed between the prosthesis and the neotympanic membrane, whereas with the hydroxyapatite prosthesis, cartilage was not used between the prosthesis and the neotympanic membrane.

The following parameters were studied to compare the results: Mean Pure Tone (MPT) using tonal audiometry and the air-bone gap (ABG). In addition, the difference between preoperative and postoperative results was evaluated by subtracting the postoperative result from the preoperative one.

Postoperative effectiveness of surgical treatment was considered satisfactory if at least one of the following criteria was met: 1) MPT gain ≤ 30 dB after surgery; 2) the difference between preoperative and postoperative ABG ≥ 15 dB; 3) Endoscopy showed whether the material was extruded.

Research Results: A one-stage ossiculoplasty was performed on 35 patients. Among them, 20 (57.1%) had CSOM with cholesteatoma, and 15 (60%) had CSOM without cholesteatoma. The average preoperative pure tone audiometry score was 47.6 ± 20.4 dB, and the air-bone gap (ABG) was 28.1 ± 13.3 dB, respectively. Of the total number of patients, 39 (65%) underwent a partial ossicular replacement prosthesis (PORP), while 21 (35%) underwent a total ossicular replacement prosthesis (TORP). Titanium and hydroxyapatite prostheses were used in 33 (55%) and 27 (45%) cases, respectively. Two-stage ossiculoplasty was performed on 25 patients, whose characteristics are presented in the following tables (Tables 1 and 2).

Table 1

Frequency of operations based on the type of pathology and type of prosthesis

Diagnosis	One-Stage Ossiculoplasty n=35		Two-Stage Ossiculoplasty n=25	
	Abs	%	Abs	%
Tubotympanic CSOM	15	42.8%	10	40.0%
Epitympanoantral CSOM	20	57.1%	15	60.0%
Type of Prosthesis				

Diagnosis	One-Stage Ossiculoplasty n=35		Two-Stage Ossiculoplasty n=25	
	PORP	22	62.8%	17
TORP	13	37.2%	8	32.0%
Type of Material				
Titanium	19	54.2%	14	56.0%
Hydroxyapatite	16	45.7%	11	44.0%

Table 2

Average Pure Tone Audiometry Scores in CSOM Patients Before Surgical Treatment

Pure Tone Audiometry	One-Stage Ossiculoplasty n=35	Two-Stage Ossiculoplasty n=25
	M±m	M±m
Mean Pure Tone (MPT)	42.6±15.4 dB	45.6±17.7 dB
ABG	26.1±13.3 dB	28.1±18.3 dB

In evaluating one-stage ossiculoplasty, the functional outcomes based on three postoperative hearing improvement criteria showed no differences depending on the material used (titanium, hydroxyapatite) or the type of prosthesis used for ossiculoplasty (PORP, TORP) in patients with CSOM with or without cholesteatoma.

A comparative analysis was conducted between different forms of CSOM—tubotympanic without cholesteatoma and epitympanoantral with cholesteatoma, as well as between different materials—titanium and hydroxyapatite within these groups. The analysis showed that there was no significant difference in the results between these groups, except for a statistically significant difference in the air-bone gap for PORP between titanium and hydroxyapatite ($p=0.04$) in patients with CSOM without cholesteatoma. The total prosthesis (TORP) was used less frequently, in 4 cases with CSOM without cholesteatoma. Additionally, regardless of the type of material used, the results for PORP were statistically significantly better than the success rate for TORP ($p<0.05$). In CSOM with cholesteatoma, PORP showed better results than TORP. Although there was no significant difference in the success rates between titanium and hydroxyapatite prostheses, there was a statistically significant difference in the mean pure tone (MPT) before and after surgery for PORP between titanium and hydroxyapatite prostheses ($p<0.05$).

In our study, the effectiveness of using titanium and hydroxyapatite for partial ossicular replacement prosthesis (PORP) in ossiculoplasty was 62.5% and 68.4%, respectively, in CSOM with cholesteatoma. The effectiveness of titanium and hydroxyapatite total ossicular replacement prosthesis (TORP) was 43.7% and 48.8%, respectively, in CSOM with cholesteatoma. The effectiveness of titanium and hydroxyapatite PORP was 80.7% and 86.3%, respectively, in CSOM without cholesteatoma.

The pure tone audiometry data after one-stage and two-stage tympanoplasty in patients with CSOM show that one-stage tympanoplasty with ossiculoplasty in CSOM is highly effective, and its functional hearing outcomes are comparable to those of two-stage ossiculoplasty based on audiological data ($P>0.05$).

Furthermore, to compare the impact of these types of surgical treatments on the quality of life (QoL), we evaluated them using the COMOT-15 questionnaire. The results showed that one-

stage tympanoplasty has a better effect on QoL than two-stage tympanoplasty. According to the questionnaire, the questions related to ear symptoms and hearing function did not differ significantly between the groups, but the third group of questions related to the psychological state of the patients showed significant differences (Table 3).

Table 3

Comparative Evaluation of QoL Based on COMOT-15 for One-Stage and Two-Stage Tympanoplasty in CSOM

COMOT-15	One-Stage Tympanoplasty (n=42)	Two-Stage Tympanoplasty (n=25)	P
Ear Symptoms (ES)			
Ear discharge	0	0	0
Ear pain	0.15±0.7	0.14±0.9	P>0.05
Ear congestion	0.18±0.9	0.17±0.7	P>0.05
Tinnitus	1.2±0.7	1.1±0.9	P>0.05
Headaches	0.75±0.09	0.87±0.08	P>0.05
ES Total	0.9±0.08	0.5±0.07	P>0.05
Hearing Function (HF)			
Hearing loss	0.3±0.06	0.4±0.06	P>0.05
Speech clarity issues over distance	0.4±0.08	0.5±0.09	P>0.05
Speech clarity issues in noisy environments	0.3±0.9	0.4±0.09	P>0.05
Speech clarity issues in group conversations	0.1±0.07	0.1±0.09	P>0.05
Hearing loss causing communication problems	0.1±0.05	0.1±0.07	P>0.05
HF Total	0.2±0.06	0.3±0.05	P>0.05
Mental Health (MH)			
Hearing loss causing discomfort	0	0	0
Fear due to ear disease	0	0	0
Impact of ear disease on QoL	0.2±0.08	1.2±0.15	P<0.001
Marking all ear-related visits in the last 6 months	0.1±0.08	1.8±0.8	P<0.05
Doctor visits in the last 6 months due to ear disease	0.1±0.08	1.8±0.8	P<0.05
MH Total	0.15±0.07	1.6±0.4	P<0.001
Overall Score	0.4±0.08	0.4±0.06	P>0.05

Note: *- significant differences relative to the pre-surgical CSOM group (P<0.05, ** P<0.01, *** P<0.001), differences relative to the post-surgical group are not significant (P>0.05).

Summary of Results: The study indicates that one-stage ossiculoplasty, whether in the presence of cholesteatoma or not, is highly effective, with functional hearing outcomes comparable to those of two-stage ossiculoplasty. However, patients undergoing two-stage surgery face the burden of two operations, severe hearing loss until the second stage, and more frequent doctor visits and longer follow-up periods. This situation also leads to increased socio-economic losses.

From the surgeon's perspective, performing one-stage tympanoplasty with ossiculoplasty is preferable if it can achieve similar functional hearing outcomes as two-stage ossiculoplasty. Moreover, if hearing improvement is not achieved after the one-stage surgery, a revision re-ossiculoplasty can be performed. Therefore, for immediate postoperative hearing improvement, inflammatory tissue removal and ossiculoplasty were carried out simultaneously during the first stage.

Contrary to previously published studies that suggest PORP and TORP yield similar results, our research found that the functional outcomes of PORP were significantly better than TORP. These findings suggest that TORP is performed in more severe middle ear conditions, such as stapes superstructure erosion.

Conclusions: Performing one-stage tympanoplasty with ossiculoplasty is preferable if it can achieve comparable hearing results to two-stage ossiculoplasty. The study results showed that partial prostheses (PORP) were significantly more effective than total prostheses (TORP). This indicates that TORP is typically used in more severe cases of middle ear disease, such as stapes structure erosion.

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